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Cross River State, Nigeria: A Global Visual Cultural and Forest Biodiversity Tourism Destination

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ABSTRACT

The evidence of Cross River State in Nigeria as a global visual cultural, biodiversity and wildlife tourism distinction located in West Africa is presented using photo-inventory. A socio-scientific photo-sourcing and explanation was carried out. The ancient city of Calabar that received early Christian missionaries to Nigeria is the capital of Cross River State in Nigeria, West Africa now host the Africa's annual biggest street party (Calabar carnival). The ancient house of Mary Mitchell Slessor a Scottish missionary to Nigeria who stopped the ancient practice of killing of twins and multiple births built in 1848, stands in Calabar as a monument that attracts tourists from all parts of the world. The international Ekpe masquerade, boat and canoe race in Calabar, Ibibio new yam festival in Ugep, Central Cross River are tourists attracted festivals. Being home of tropical forest with rare biodiversity added with wildlife, some mammals as endangered Gorilla, drill, chimpanzee and African black elephants, including different species of African Primates are seen in the protected zones of the National Park and Afi Wildlife Sanctuary. Photos of numerous huge ancient carved and engraved standing stones (Monoliths) dating back to 1200 BC are found in about 30 communities in Ikom, the Central part of Cross River State of Nigeria. Spectacular natural waterfalls for relaxation are in existence. The Obudu mountain Resort city exhibit the four weather type witness in Europe and America. The Resort is located on a mountain 1600 m high in the Northern Cross River State. Photos of the winding road from the bottom of the mountain to the top and nature dug swimming pools are places to visit.

Keywords: Monoliths, Street party, Tourism, Calabar carnival, Wildlife, Biodiversity, endangered animals, Cross River State

INTRODUCTION

Cross River State of Nigeria nicknamed the "People's Paradise" by the government is located in West Africa and shares a common border with the Republic of Cameroon, a country situated in the Central part of Africa. The state derives its name from Cross River, a river that originates from the mountains in the Cameroons and flows into the State in Nigeria. The capital of the state is known as Calabar (Calabar is fondly interpreted as "come and live and be at rest"). It is fondly referred to as Canaan city, after Canaan in Galilee in Israel as a city flowing with milk and honey.

Old Calabar had contact with Europeans traders (Germans and Portuguese in the 17th century as well as hosting early Christian missionaries to Nigeria in 1843. The residence of Mary Slessor who arrived Calabar in 1875 standing as a monument and ancient visual cultural tourism sites to visit and relax. The Afi Wildlife Sanctuary and Cross River National Park are forest and game reserves that host a lot of wildlife and biodiversity. The Kwa River and Kwa waterfall in the southern part of the State and Agbokim waterfall in the Central part of the State are natural places to behold.

The Cross River State Monoliths found in Ikom the central part of the State is a unique form of African visual creativity and they typify a traditional art genre defined by minimalism aesthetics. The Ikom Monoliths date could trace back to 1200 BC to 200 AD. Some of the

Monoliths are carved from hard stones derived from volcanic rock 'basalt'. These stones (Monoliths) are creatively decorated with carvings, stylized human features, and given various kinds of facial marks.

While some are carved from sandstone and limestone. The Obudu Mountain Resort is on a plateau of 1600 m high. It is said to be the most visited tourism destination in Nigeria and West Africa. It has all the weather seasons found in Europe (spring, summer, winter, and autumn). The spiral zig-zag road network takes people from the bottom up the mountain. At the top of the Mountain Resort are small mountains beautiful to behold with calm weather and a serene natural environment with nature dug swimming pools maintained by man. The book presents photos of cultural activities, Africa's biggest street party (Calabar carnival), international cultural festivals, rare wildlife species still found in tropical forest.

THE POPULAR MARY MITCHELL SLESSOR HOUSE IN CALABAR

Photo 1 depicts the building where Mary Mitchell Slessor lived in Calabar from her time of arrival in 1875 until she died January 13, 1915, which is now a tourist attraction centre in Calabar, Nigeria. The National Museum and Monument in Nigeria now manages the structure as a monument. Mary Slessor was a Scottish missionary who served in Old Calabar. She ended the practice of killing twins and multiple birth children and treating their mothers as pariah, which had been practiced for centuries.

Before her arrival from Scotland, in Calabar and other regions of Nigeria, twin birth was thought to be a bad omen. The father of one of the infants (twins) was thought to be an evil spirit, and the mother had committed a major transgression against the gods of the land. Because people couldn't tell which twin was fathered by the evil spirit, the natives would frequently abandon twin's babies and multiple birth children and their mothers in the forest to die alongside their mothers. Mary Slessor preached against this act and saved the babies and their mothers. She adopted the children as her children and care for their mothers.

CALABAR BOAT REGATTA

The Calabar carnival, Africa's largest street party, is a one-month daily event held in December in Calabar, the capital of Cross River State, Nigeria, West Africa (Figure 1). A day is set aside for each activity, and each group is assigned a certain day to perform. A day is also set aside for competitive boat/canoe races (regatta). **Photos 2 to 9** show the display boat and canoe regatta and events. The competitive boat race takes place in the Calabar River. The Efik tribe of Old Calabar used to hold a ceremonial boat racing as part of the ceremony when a new King was crowned (Obong of Calabar and Treaty King). Boat regattas were jointly held by all Efik tribes to commemorate their conquest in tribal conflicts in ancient times.

A competitive boat regatta introduced as a competitive social entertainment event with a tourism component. It draws tourists, visitors and friends of the Efik, Efut, and Qua tribes from all around Nigeria and outside. Beautifully adorned boats and canoes can be seen in **Photos 2 to 9**, with beautifully dressed boat and canoe paddlers. This is demonstrating how the traditional ceremonial boat racing has evolved into a visual arts event that attracts tourists and boosts local and national businesses.

Photos 8 and 9 show masquerades in a boat and a canoe, which were brought by contesting groups to celebrate and applaud them as supporters club.

EKPE MASQUERADES (NYORO EKPE) INTERNATIONAL FESTIVAL

The Efiks are noted for their luxurious masquerades, the most prestigious of which is the Ekpe. Calabar's Ekpe masquerade (Efik, Efut, and Qua Kingdoms) is a tourist attraction and spectacle. Tourists have taken images of the Ekpe masquerade for postcards, tourism advertisements, and other uses. The careful color combinations of red, black, yellow, white, and other raffias woven together with Ekpe masquerade fabric as seen in **Photos 10 - 23** by the various forms of Ekpe masquerades. Ekombi singer and dancer (**Photo 24**). **Photo 25** depicts a young Ekpe Socio-cultural Society initiate, while **Photo 26** depicts an antique wooden drum that is only used during important Ekpe traditional ceremonial traditional activities. **Photos 27 - 33** depict dancers dressed in traditional chieftaincy shirts and wrappers performing to the accompaniment of drums and vocalists, much to the delight of visitors and spectators.

Nnabo masquerades in various colours and from various socio-cultural groups are shown in **Photos 34 - 48**. The Ekpe international festival, also known as *nyoro* in the local community, is the world's most popular masquerade. It's an Ekpe Socio-Cultural Society masquerade. Ekpe masquerades from the Caribbeans, Cuba, Brazil, the United States, the Caribbean, and Cameroun all visit the annual celebration and participate in full traditional regalia. The ancestors of Africans who were transported across the Atlantic as slaves (Efik of Cross River State and Akwa Ibom States of Nigeria) are still maintaining the Ekpe Society and culture.

LEBOKU AGRO FESTIVAL

Another international tourism agro event from the Ugep, Yakurr in the Central part of Cross River State is the leboku new yam festival (**Figure 1**). It is a three-week annual celebration in which people honour the goddess and ancestral spirit of the land for providing a bountiful crop to the people and community. **Photos 49 - 71** shows young and old, men, leg-girdle maidens and women celebrating the leboku new yam festival in beautiful traditional attire.

THE AFRICA'S BIGGEST STREET PARTY

The Calabar carnival in Nigeria, also known as "Africa's Biggest Street Party" is an annual event held in December in Calabar, the capital city of Cross River State. The ancient city of Calabar (**Figure 1**) was the first capital of Nigeria known then as the Oil River Protectorate and Niger Coast Protectorate. It houses the British colonial administration in Nigeria from the 18th to early 20th century. The colonial relics can still be found all over the city including the colonial names that dominate the streets in the city. These relics attract tourists from Europe to the city. Photos of some events during the Calabar carnival or Africa's biggest street party are presented in **Photos 72 - 89**. The carnival started in 2004 and is held every December during the Christmas celebration. The carnival attracts international tourists from all parts of the world.

The colours, costumes, and potentials of the rich African culture are displayed at a street party as shown in **Photos 72 - 89**.

Special invitations are extended to cultural troops from other African countries, the Caribbean, and Southern America, Cuba. Participants from different parts of Africa and elsewhere around the globe wear and present different special costumes, colours, culture, and traditions in a happy and joyful-minded carnival float. From 2004 the carnival has grown and expanded to become an international festival and Nigeria's number one biggest street party. Many countries in Africa now travel to participate in the carnival displaying their special costumes and traditions in the street party.

NATURE, BIODIVERSITY AND WILDLIFE CONSERVATION IN CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

Wildlife conservation in the Cross River State of Nigeria is an important aspect of the environmental protection program. The Cross River National Park managed by The Federal Government of Nigeria and Afi Wildlife Sanctuary managed by the Cross River State Forestry Commission are Nigeria's only National Park with a tropical rain forest. The park and the Sanctuary covers mangrove swamps to the coastal areas with the forest being crisscrossed by rivers and little streams. The Cross River National Park covers a terrain of about 4,000 km².

The National Park preserves the last remnants of the fauna and flora in this magnificent rain forest with some of the wildlife found in the park shown in **Photos 72 - 99**. By doing this, the Park endorses eco-tourism in Nigeria. The National Park and the Afi Wildlife Sanctuary provide unlimited opportunities to experience the biologically varied host of many species of plants and animals. Rare species of baboons and gorillas dwell in the Cross River National Park making it one of the ultimate tourist destinations for those wanting to spend some time with these glorious animals. Other striking animals found in the park and wildlife sanctuary are buffaloes, forest elephants, chimpanzees, manatees, and other monkeys of various shades and species. The Agbokim waterfall with seven falls (**Photo 101**) and Kwafall (**Photo 100**) with 234 natural stairs (steps) to go up the fall from the bottom are sites to behold.

THE IKOM MONOLITHS OF 1200 BC TO 200 AD IN CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

Ikom is a town in the Central part of Cross River State, southeast Nigeria (**Figure 1**), only 30 km from the border with the Republic of Cameroon. It has about 30 surrounding communities or villages that harbour very magnificent mysterious stones carvings and some standing engraved stones known as the Ikom Monoliths as seen in **Photos 102 to 147**. The Ikom Monoliths are a series of volcanic-stone Monoliths from Ikom in Cross River State, Nigeria. The age of the engraving on the Monoliths was traced to between the sixteenth and twentieth century. Most of the Monoliths are upright-standing stones found in various sizes. The stones are nicely carved, dressed and smoothed. The heights vary from 0.6 to 1.8 m and widths of 0.6 to 0.9 m.

The beautiful decoration of the Monoliths is a wonder to tourists when one considers the date and age of the Monoliths. Most of the stones are engraved with the shape of a stylized face

on top, signifying kings that were considered brave. Some of the faces on the Monoliths are believed to represent gods, or those who rule on behalf of the gods, the kings. There are about 450 Monoliths of over 1500 years old that have been counted and documented.

THE SLAVE HISTORY MUSEUM

Using visual the Slave Museum communicates the historical activities of the slave trade era of the 18th century in Old Calabar, Nigeria. **Photos 148, 149** and **150** present the Slave Museum. The slave warehouse located beside the Calabar River has been converted to a slave history Museum. The Museum has artistic depictions of slave trade activities and events as shown in **Photo 149**.

The relics of tools, equipment and materials used then to facilitate slave trade are also seen in display in the museum. For slaves reaching the warehouse by the Calabar River meant coming to the “point of no return”. From the warehouse by the port, slaves were ferried to Europe and America. The slave history museum attracts tourist from around the world as it display visually the unadulterated history of slave trade in this part of the world.

OBUDU MOUNTAIN RESORT

The Obudu mountain resort, historically known as the Obudu cattle ranch, is a 1600 m high plateau settlement. It is the most beautiful and enjoyable tourist attraction place in the world (**Photos 151** and **152**). The twisting constructed road that leads from the mountain's base to its top is motorable and a site to behold and travel along (**Photo 152**). The cable cab (**Photo 153**) transports tourists and visitors from the mountain's base to the top. The stunning natural bathing pools (**Photo 151**) are a sight to behold and accommodation in the resort are of world-class standard.

CONCLUSIONS

Cross River State, Nigeria in West Africa is a tourism destination in Nigeria and West Africa. When on visit, places of historical, cultural festivals and activities, wildlife and biodiversity interest abound. They include but are not limited to the few mentioned. A house built in 1848, housed Mary Slessor a Scottish Christian Missionary who saved and stopped the ancient practice of killing of twins and multiple birth in Nigeria. The international Ekpe masquerade festival brings Efik descendants from the United States, Cuba, Latin America and Caribbean to Calabar their ancestral home from where their ancestors were sold as slaves. The Ikom new yam festival is an annual three week festival to watch and participate in.

The Africa's biggest street party (Calabar carnival) is the hallmark of tourism activities and this is held every December in the State. The National Park and Wildlife Sanctuary houses endangered animal and plant species. The natural Agbokim waterfall with seven falls and kwafalls with 234 natural stairs (steps) to go up the fall from the bottom are sites to behold. The Ikom Monoliths that dates back to 1200 BC display the artistic mysterious works to behold.

The Obudu Mountain Resort is situated on a plateau 1600 m high and its winding road from the bottom of the mountain to the top is a sight to behold.

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Figure 1. Cross River State, Nigeria, West Africa showing all the Local Government Areas including Calabar, Akamkpa, Ugep, Ikom and Obudu as centre of tourism activities

Photo 1. The famous Mary Mitchill Slessor House in Calabar, Nigeria built in 1848. She was a Scottish and Missionary to Calabar, Nigeria who stopped the ancient tradition of killing twins and multiple births in Calabar and Nigeria.

Source: nigeriagalleria

BOAT REGATTA IN CALABAR, NIGERIA

Photo 2. Boat regatta in Calabar River in Calabar, Cross River State in West Africa.

Photo 3. Boat regatta in warming up for water racing in Calabar River during the Calabar Carnival.

Photo 4. Different boat contestants ready for start of boat regatta in Calabar

Photo 5. Boat regatta with contesting boats on the river.

Photo 6. A boat and canoe men warming up for boat regatta in Calabar River in Nigeria

Photo 7. Boat racing (regatta) in action in Calabar River, Nigeria

Photo 8. Calabar masquerade and drum men and singers in a boat in the river adding colour to the boat regatta

Photo 9. Ekpe masquerade and drum men in a boat in the river adding colour to the boat regatta

INTERNATIONAL MASQUERADES FESTIVAL IN CALABAR CARNIVAL AND STREET PARTY

Photo 10. Efik masquerade prepared using dry plantain leaves. It is said to be the first and oldest respectable masquerade in Old Calabar

Photo 11. Ekpe masquerade in cultural display during the Ekpe masquerade festival in Calabar

Photo 12. An Ekpe masquerade in Calabar in a traditional dance display.

Photo 13. Line up of Ekpe masquerades of the Efik Kingdom in cultural dance display during ekpe cultural festival

Photo 14. Ekpe masquerade presented by one of the Royal Houses of Efik kingdom in Calabar.

Photo 15. Women from one of the Efik Royal Houses in Calabar in a cultural display.

Photo 16. Two different shed of Ekpe masquerade in a cultural display.

Photo 17. Ekpe masquerade presented by one of the Royal House in Efik Kingdom

Photo 18. Ekpe masquerade from one of the Royal House in Efik Kingdom in a cultural dance display.

Photo 19. Ekpe masquerade in a cultural dance display.

Photo 20. Ekpe masquerade in dance display

Photo 21. Ekpe masquerade presented by a Royal House in Calabar.

Photo 22. Another type of Ekpe masquerade in a dance display during the Ekpe cultural festival.

Photo 23. A Calabar masquerade in a dance display during a cultural festival in Calabar.

Photo 24. The Efik male traditional costume in display during a cultural festival

Photo 25. A young Ekpe initiate and traditional drum.

Photo 26. A traditional wooden drum used for drumming in the Efik Kingdom in Calabar.

Photo 27. A cultural masquerade house in open display during the cultural festival in Calabar.

Photo 28. A masquerade that rises tall and shorten simultaneously.

Photo 29. A cultural masquerade house in the cultural festival in Calabar

Photo 30. Efik men in cultural display.

Photo 31. Efik men in traditional wrapper and chieftaincy shirts in festival cultural dance display.

Photo 32. Efik men in traditional wrapper, chieftaincy shirts and walking sticks in festival cultural dance display.

Photo 33. Efik Chiefs in festival cultural dance display.

Photo 34. Efik *Nnabo* masquerade in a cultural dance during a cultural festival in Calabar

Photo 35. Efik *Nnabo* masquerade in a cultural dance during a cultural festival in Calabar

Photo 36. Efik *Nnabo* masquerade in a cultural dance during a cultural festival in Calabar

Photo 37. Efik *Nnabo* masquerades in colourful cultural dance during a cultural festival in Calabar

Photo 38. Efik *Nnabo* masquerade in a cultural dance during a cultural festival in Calabar

Photo 39. Efik *Nnabo* masquerades in different colours in cultural festival in Calabar

Photo 40. Efik *Nnabo* masquerades in different colours displaying in a cultural festival in Calabar

Photo 41. Efik *Nnabo* masquerades in a cultural dance during a cultural festival in Calabar

Photo 42. Women and a man in Efik tribe traditional dance consume in a street party in Calabar. The Efiks are tribe in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria

Photo 43. Women and a man in Efik tribe traditional dance consume in a Cultural carnival.

Photo 44. An Efik maiden dressed in a traditional attire during a cultural festival

Photo 45. An Efik maiden display Efik maiden traditional attire.

Photo 46. An Efik maiden in a traditional attire during a cultural festival

Photo 47. An Efik maiden dressed in an Efik traditional attire during a cultural festival

Photo 48. An Efik maiden display the colourful madien traditional attire during a cultural festival

LEBOKU (NEW YAM FESTIVAL) IN UGEP, CENTRAL CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

Photo 49. Leboku (new yam festival) Priest in Ugep, Central Cross River State, Nigeria

Photo 50. Leboku traditional ceremony before to kick start the new yam festival

Photo 51. Leboku Chiefs performing traditional rites during the Leboku festival

Photo 52. Leboku Chiefs in different colours during the festival

Photo 53. The Leboku dance during the Leboku festival in Ugep, Central Cross River State.

Photo 54. The Leboku maidens in different traditional colours with yams tie in robe behind

Photo 55. A joyous time during Leboku festival

Photo 56. A jousous time during Leboku festival

Photo 57. A maiden in Leboku tradional attire

Photo 58. Display of traditional dancing steps during Leboku festival

Photo 59. A Leboku maiden in joyous time

Photo 60. Performance and joyous moment during leboku festival

Photo 61. Dressed in traditional attire.

Photo 62. Joyous traditional dancing display during the leboku festival

Photo 63. Leboku performance with robe of yams traditional attire.

Photo 64. Men in joyous moment and performance in leboku festival

Photo 65. Leg bangle leboku maiden in a joyous parading in town during the festival

Photo 66. Leg-bangle ILeboku maiden in traditional attire during the festival

Photo 67. Young men, children and leboku maiden parade the town.

Photo 68. Leg-bangle wearing leboku maidens in joyous mode parade the town

Photo 69. Atmosphere of leboku celebration in town of Ugep, Cross River State, Nigeria, as visitors, tourists, young maiden, young men in traditional costumes and plain cloths parade the street in joy and the spirit of celebration

Photo 70. Youths in streets and in joyous mode during the leboku festival

Photo 71. Winners of 2021 Mr Leboku and Miss Lekoku

CALABAR CARNIVAL (AFRICA'S BIGGEST STREET PARTY)

Photo 72. Calabar carnival costume

Photo 73. Government officials in Calabar cut the tape to declared the carnival open

Photo 74. Joyous moment in Calabar carnival

Photo 75. Leader of a carnival group in Calabar carnival and street party

Photo 76. A calabar carnival queen in carnival street party

Photo 77. The traditional female dance of the traditional Cross River State of Nigeria.
Source: Canivaland (2019)

Photo 78. A street parade of the Female carnival dance in the street of Calabar of Cross River State, Nigeria.
Source: Canivaland (2019)

Photo 79. The Street dance of the traditional culture carnival in Calabar, capital city of Cross River State, Nigeria
Source: Canivaland (2019)

Photo 80. The Kenyan costume display at the street party carnival in Calabar, Nigeria
Source: Canivaland (2019)

Photo 81. The Female carnival dance with the Western costume in Calabar street party in Nigeria.
Source: Canivaland (2019)

Photo 82. Children display of a Tanzanian traditional costume displayed in the Calabar, Nigeria Street Party

Source: Canivaland (2019)

Photo 83. Out of fattening room costume of the traditional old Calabar. A tradition that have been brought into the modern age

Source: Canivaland (2019)

Photo 84. The happy participants in Calabar Carnival Street dance
Source: Canivaland (2019)

Photo 85. A cultural display of the northern Cross River State culture
Source: Canivaland (2019)

Photo 86. A display of the Egyptian culture, and the face of an African woman in a Street move at Calabar Carnival
Source: Canivaland (2019)

Photo 87. Beauty Pageant and Musical Artist performing at a night show at the Calabar Carnival
Source: Canivaland (2019)

Photo 88. The traditional African Culture of Kenya (up) and (Tanzania) displayed at a street walk at the Calabar Carnival in Nigeria
Source: Canivaland (2019)

Photo 89. The Benin culture of Nigeria been display in a Street Party at Calabar, Nigeria
Source: Canivaland (2019)

**WILDLIFE OF NATIONAL PARK AND AFI WILDLIFE SANCTUARY IN
AKAMKPA IN SOUTHERN CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA**

Photo 90. An endangered Gorilla at the Cross River National Park
Source: newsroom.wcs.org

Photo 91. The primate of Africa, with indigenous origin in the rainforest of tropical Africa.
Source: [nigeriaparkservice](https://nigeriaparkservice.com)

Photo 92. The natural environment where the wildlife of Cross River State exist
Source: nigeriaparkservice

Photo 93. An African elephant in the Cross River National Park in Nigeria
Source: nigeriaparkservice

Photo 94. The Africa elephant in group search for food in the National Park in tropical rainforest, Nigeria, Africa
Source: nigeriaparkservice

Photo 95. The black African Elephant in search for water to drink
Source: nigeriagalleria

Photo 96. The bridge of Ikom in Nigeria to Republic of Cameroon. This bridge was made for emergency crossing, and has today been used for the attraction of tourist and for the exploration of the nature of the area

Source: nigeriaparkservice

Photo 97. The view of the primate species that have undergone evolution over time in the Park

Source: nigeriaparkservice

Photo 98. The Primate of the tropical Africa that lives in the region of Cross River State, Nigeria
Source: Source: nigeriaparkservice

Photo 99. The Indigenous primate of Africa, that exist in the tropical Africa and found in Cross River State, Nigeria

Photo 100. Kwa falls that exist in the landmass of Cross River State of Nigeria
Source: hotels.ng

Photo 101. Agbokim waterfall, that exist in Ikom, Nigeria
Source: hotels.ng

Photo 102. The Monoliths of Ikom, Cross River State of Nigeria holds this heritage of the past, and brings it into the present. It can be likened to the sun religion of the old kingdom of Egypt.

Photo 103. Each of the Monoliths in Ikom, Nigeria represent each tradition, culture, religion including the time-past events and happenings.

Sourece: artsymoments.com

Photo 104. The Monoliths in Ikom, Cross River State in Nigeria
Source: pinterest.com

Photo 105. The Monoliths in Ikom representing the heritage and culture of the people of Ikom in Central Cross River State, Nigeria
Source: semanticscholar.org

Photo 106. The heritage of the culture and tradition of the Ikom people of central Cross River State
Source: networks.h-net.org

Photo 107. The Ikom, Cross River State, Nigeria Monoliths in yard as point of trace for the sun religion worship back in the early history of the Egyptian culture
Source: [pinterest.com](https://www.pinterest.com)

Photo 108. The variety of Monoliths of Ikom in Cross River State.
Source: pinterest.com

Photo 109. Monoliths artefact preserved in the indoor of the museum of Calabar.
Source: pinterest.com

Photo 110. Monoliths carefully preserved in a wooden stand.
Source: wmf.org

Photo 111. Immortalizing the existence of personalities in Monoliths for the transmission of culture and tradition
Source: britishmuseum.org

Photo 112. The face and immortalization of the culture and tradition of the Ikom people of Cross River State, Nigeria.
Source: facebook

Photo 108. The Ikom, Cross River State, Nigeria Monoliths in yard as point of trace for the sun religion worship back in the early history of the Egyptian culture
Source: pinterest.com

Photo 113. A Monolith near the village of Alok in Ikom, Cross River State, Nigeria, West Africa. The Monolith is dated back to 1200 BC - 200 AD,
Source: Weate, (2006)

Photo 114. A Monolith near the village of Alok in Ikom, Cross River State, Nigeria, West Africa. The Monolith is dated back to 1200 BC - 200 AD,
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Photo 115. Monoliths near the village of Alok in Ikom, Cross River State, Nigeria, West Africa.
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Photo 124. Monoliths near the village of Alok in Ikom, Cross River State, Nigeria, West Africa. The Monolith is dated back to 1200 BC - 200 AD.

Source: Weate, (2006)

Photo 125. An Ikom Monolith near the village of Alok. (1200 BC-200 AD, Cross River State, SE Nigeria)

Source: Weate, J., (2006)

Photo 126. A Monolith near the village of Alok in Ikom, Cross River State, Nigeria, West Africa. The Monolith is dated back to 1200 BC - 200 AD.
Source: Weate, (2006)

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Photo 146. A Monolith near the village of Alok in Ikom, Cross River State, Nigeria, West Africa. The Monolith is dated back to 1200 BC - 200 AD,
Source: Weate, (2006)

Photo 147. Chief S.E. Akong besides an Ikom Monolith near the village of Alok in Cross River State Nigeria, West Africa.
Source: De Jonge and Wakefield (2002)

THE SLAVE HISTORY OF OLD CALABAR

Photo 148. Slave museum located by the Calabar river where ship berth and ferry slaves to Europe

Photo 149. Slave warehouse now converted to slave to museum in Calabar, Nigeria, The Museum sits beside the Calabar River where Slaves were shipped to Great Britain.

Source: pulse.org

Photo 150. Depiction of slave trade era of the 15th century in Calabar at the Slave Museum in Calabar, Nigeria, West Africa
Source: ayomarcars.com

**THE OBUDU MOUNTAIN RESORT IN NORTHERN CROSS RIVER STATE,
NIGERIA, WEST AFRICA**

Photo 151. Natural swimming pool at Obudu Mountain Resort in Cross River State, Nigeria situated at height of 1600 m. This pool exist in the rainforest zone of tropical Africa.
Source: [facebook.com/Obudu-Cattle-Ranch](https://www.facebook.com/Obudu-Cattle-Ranch)

Photo 152. Winding road to Obudu Mountain Resort situated 1600 m above sea-level in Cross River State. It has a temperate climate.
Source: [yellowurban.com](https://www.yellowurban.com)

Photo 153. Cable car of 850 m height from foot of mountain to Obudu Mountain Resort at the top

Source: nigeriagalleria.com